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Dissemination plan- first version

CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD PROJECT

Document information

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Executive summary

This document constitutes the first version of the Dissemination plan (D7.2) of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project, elaborated under Task 7.1 Dissemination & Communication of Work Package 7 Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Business Planning.

CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD is a HORIZON 2020 project aiming to build an mHealth application that improves the Quality of Life of people living with dementia and their caregivers. The application will integrate a broader diagnostic approach, incorporating the caregiver-patient dyad and considering this dyad as the unit of care. The application will provide value-added services based on social networks, tailored interventions, clinical strategies and gamification for improving quality of life for people living with dementia and caregivers that allow them to live in the community for as long as possible.

The document describes the overall awareness raising process, the management and monitoring of the dissemination activities and partners responsibilities. It includes specific actions and activities that will be carried out by the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD consortium members in order to ensure success and maximum publicity for the project and its results.

It outlines:

- The targeted audiences, namely those who are relevant to and may benefit from project activities,
- The communication tools/instruments to disseminate to the targeted groups, and
- The time plan for disseminating project results, including consortium responsibilities and relevant work packages and milestones

WP7 leader Q-PLAN will closely monitor the implementation of the actions described in the present document.

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Title
DoA	Description of the Action
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
EC	European Community
EEN	European Enterprise Network
EU	European Union
NCP	National Contact Point

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1 Introduction

The current Dissemination Plan has been developed by Q-PLAN International with the purpose to be the main frame of reference for CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project partners on their promotion and communication tasks.

The main objective of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD Dissemination Plan is to create and enhance awareness on CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD activities and results on defined target groups (see § 3 Dissemination target groups), thus helping to achieve the success of the project, in line with the contractual obligations that the consortium has undertaken with the EC.

More specific targets of the document include:

- To describe the various types of dissemination tools to be implemented and the required actions and resources,
- To define responsibilities among partners,
- To summarize the internal monitoring, evaluation and reporting of dissemination activities, and
- To provide an indicative timetable/ work planning of promotion activities during the project.

It should be noted that the level of impact of all publicity actions described in this document relies on the active participation of all consortium partners.

Remark: The analysis of dissemination tools, actions and plans will become more detailed in the next versions of Dissemination plan of the project, as the development and testing of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD application evolves and of with the implementation of the pilots.

2 Management of the Dissemination Plan

The Dissemination Plan is produced by the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Leader (Q-PLAN) under work package 7 and is approved by the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project coordinator (UPC). Q-PLAN is responsible for updating or changing the Dissemination Plan, when necessary. In any case, a second updated version of the Dissemination Plan will be delivered in June 2017 (M18 of the project) according to DoA.

Before a new version is put into force, a draft version is sent by Q-PLAN to all partners for comments. Q-PLAN takes into account the comments of the partners, finalizes the new version of the Dissemination Plan and releases the new version, after the approval of UPC, as Project Coordinator.

CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD partners are expected to comply with the dissemination plan, thus they are expected to identify all dissemination activities they have to carry out and ensure their high quality. Partners are also responsible for adapting the dissemination activities to their countries (*i.e.* at national level) and for performing effective monitoring and follow up of their publicity activities.

3 Dissemination target groups

The following target groups for project dissemination have been identified:

- **Scientific community (with R&D activities related to neurocognitive disorders).**
- **Dementia and Alzheimer's disease associations, networks and social media websites and communities.**
- **Healthcare professionals related to neurocognitive disorders.**
- **Policy makers in the field of health and social care.**
- **Similar EU collaborative initiatives.**
- **Possible users (people living with dementia, informal caregivers, professional caregivers, professional social workers, dyads of people living with dementia and caregivers, healthcare professionals, etc).**

Remark: The direct engagement of possible end users is a priority for Social Network Services of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform. For this reason, the proposed actions for disseminating project results and enhancing public awareness directly to the possible end-users target group will be described in detail in D4.5 Social Media Plan. The exact definition of possible end users group will be analyzed in the first version of D7.5 Business Plan.

4 Dissemination tools

The main dissemination tools for CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project are the following:

- Project web-portal and partners web-portals,
- Project social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and partners social media accounts,
- Online newsletter and targeted recipients mailing list,
- Interaction with Social Media Networks of the platform,
- Promotional material (logo, leaflet, poster, presentation, video and promotional material for project events),
- Publications in popular and sector press/media (press releases, interviews etc.),
- Scientific publications,
- Participation in external popular events (exhibitions, business events, information days, *etc*),
- Pilot workshops,
- Participation in scientific events (conferences, *etc*),
- CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD workshops and training/demonstration sessions,
- CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD closing event,
- Synergies with other projects/initiatives,
- EU dissemination channels.

With the exploitation of the abovementioned dissemination tools, the Consortium aims to meet the following dissemination objectives:

- To present and promote effectively the project to all possible target groups/ audiences in national and European level,
- To establish links with international organizations and other interested stakeholders in order to provide wider dissemination,
- To set up liaisons with related European projects throughout H2020 project clustering,
- To validate the project outcomes, in order to obtain feedback from expert groups, scientists and interested user communities.

4.1 Project web-portal and partners web-portals

The project web-portal (<http://www.caregiversprommd-project.eu>) will be ready on month 5 (M5) of the project (May 2016) and it will constitute the main communication conduit of the project. Extensive information and news about the project and its activities, all publishable outcomes (including promotional material, scientific documents and project deliverables of public dissemination level), will be posted on the portal and made available to the general public. Links to relevant projects/initiatives, to social media accounts of the project and to project partner's webpages will also be included. A separate link will be available providing

access to demonstrations of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform (after its updated version in M25).

The web-portal will also be equipped with an online subscription tool for visitors and a mass e-mail sender tool for the dissemination of newsletters, press releases, invitations to project events etc. The news section of the web-portal will be updated at least once monthly and will be available for at least five years after the period of the grant. All partners are required to publish occasionally news of the project to the web-portals of their organizations.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the design, operation and update of the project web-portal. All partners are required to create links to the project web-portal on the websites of their organizations and to contribute with news to be uploaded. The CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD portal will be cited/mentioned in all publicity material generated by the project Consortium. The CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD portal will be cited/ mentioned in all publicity material generated by the project consortium. Finally, feedback will be asked concerning the website's appearance, contents, style and all partners should provide navigation.

4.2 Project social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and partners social media accounts

A CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD LinkedIn group, a Facebook page and a Twitter account have been created in M1 of the project as part of D7.1 deliverable. The project social media will be continuously updated in English with news about the project activities and results, various events, scientific news, news from dementia-related organizations/ associations etc. The frequency of social media posts etc. will depend on the availability of news about the activities and results of the project. In any case, the minimum frequency of posts as described in DoA will be strictly kept (Facebook –at least two posts per month, Twitter – at least one tweet per week, LinkedIn- at least one post per month).

Facebook page: Caregiverspro-Mmd project

LinkedIn group: CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD Project

Twitter: CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD (@caregiverspromd)

A YouTube channel will also be created after M16 to upload CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD promotional videos (see §3.4). Other audiovisual material related to the project (*e.g.* videos from events, interviews, TV appearances, *etc*) will also be uploaded in the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD YouTube channel.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the administration of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD social media sites. *Likes, Following* and *Group memberships* have already been made to social media pages of project partners, dementia or Alzheimer's' associations and networks, health care structures about dementia or Alzheimer's disease, EU policy makers and EU similar collaborative initiatives. All partners are required to become member or/and follower, or to actively like, the social media of the project and also to disseminate through their personal networks. Partners are also asked to interact with news, uploads, tweets and retweets, conversations and likes in the social media sites of the project, during the whole three-years duration of the

grant, as well as to publish posts/news about CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD regularly through the social media of their organizations.

4.3 Online newsletter and targeted recipients' mailing list

An online newsletter will be prepared and distributed regularly through the project website, presenting the activities and outcomes of the project, news from similar initiatives, news in the relevant scientific fields, *etc.* The frequency of newsletter issues will depend on the amount and importance of news to be presented, with the target to produce a newsletter at least every 6 months.

The initial recipients' list will be created and administered by Q-PLAN, based on desk research and existent dissemination databases. The list will be continuously updated during the project, therefore everyone who is interested will be able to subscribe to the recipients' list by registering on the project website. At the same time, recipients who do not wish to receive the newsletter will be unsubscribed by Q-PLAN. The recipients' list may also be used for the dissemination of other news, announcements, *etc.* related to the project activities.

The newsletter issues will be prepared by Q-PLAN, with the contribution of partners to the content. The content of each issue will be decided and agreed among the consortium. Partners are also required to disseminate the newsletter issues through their own dissemination channels.

4.4 Promotional material (logo, leaflet, poster, presentation, video and promotional material for project events)

Promotional material will be mainly used both at project workshops and external events where CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD partners participate. Also, it will be used in the everyday publicity of the project. All promotional material will include the project logo, the EU flag and the disclaimer, as required in Grant Agreement.

Q-PLAN will be responsible for the preparation of the graphic design and content (in English) of all printable promotional material. Each partner will be responsible for translations (if considered necessary) and printing according to its specific needs. **Partners without the previous review and approval of WP7 leader Q-PLAN should produce no kind of promotional material related to the project.**

The creation of the project logo was the responsibility of Q-PLAN and has been approved by all partners. Versions for web and print use are available for all partners in the OpenProject internal portal. A general project presentation in PowerPoint (*.ppt) format has also been created and made available to partners, to be used for project dissemination purposes in various events.

A project leaflet and a poster presenting general information on the project (aim, objectives, partners, *etc.*) will be created by M5 (May 2016) of the project. Apart from the general project leaflet and posters, specific printable promotional material for the promotion of

CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD events, of training/demonstration sessions and of pilot schemes will be prepared during the project, according to the needs of the responsible partners.

A short video, of about five minutes duration, presenting CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project as well as some short videos and demonstration of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform will be prepared after the release of the updated version of the platform in M25. The preparation of the videos is the responsibility of Q-PLAN, with the support of technical partners regarding the presentation of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform. All videos will be uploaded onto the YouTube channel of the project.

4.5 Interaction with Social Media Networks of the platform

The Social Media Networks of the platform will be created under Task 4.5, with the aim to build community capacity for the pilots. All aspects regarding the operation of the social media networks of the platform for each pilot country will be presented (goals, target audience, core topics, editorial calendar, influencer engagement, communication plan, etc) will be included in D4.5 Social Media Plan, that will be delivered in M10 (October 2016).

Frequent exchange of news, posts and tweets between the social media of the project and those of the platform will be established, under the responsibility of their respective administrators (Q-PLAN for project social media). The consortium will also examine the possibility to use the publish engine that will be developed in Task 4.5, in order to share automatically content/ posts/ news to the social media of the project.

4.6 Publications in popular/ mass media (press releases, interviews etc.) and scientific publications

All partners, will produce press and media releases, articles in popular press, presentations in TV and radio, or other media, on *ad-hoc* basis during the project, both in English and in local languages.

Scientific knowledge generated during the project will be shared in open access scientific conferences and journals.

All partners are responsible for identifying any publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure publications of project assets and conclusions. Each partner will make effort to publish in the highest quality appropriate publication, which not only reflects on the Consortiums' reputation but also on the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD initiative. All publications must cite or/and refer to the EU contribution and project grant agreement number, as required in Grant Agreement. Examples on how to comply with these requirements can be found in ANNEX 4. The requirements for scientific publications are also available in ANNEX 4.

The "CAREGIVERSPRO-Publications.xls" document will be used for keeping track of completed publications. The form of the document is shown in ANNEX 3.

4.7 Participation in external events (exhibitions, business events, information days, scientific events and conferences, etc)

The CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project team will assist and participate in various external events and networks, related to the knowledge fields of the project (dementia, mild cognitive impairment, Alzheimer's disease, geriatric medicine, etc.), as well as to EU events related to e-Health. The goals of attending these events will be to keep in touch with the latest evolutions in national and international healthcare activities, share knowledge, and establish contact and interactions with key stakeholders/policy and decision makers, while at the same time communicating CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD results.

Partners that disseminate CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project in external events should follow the respective Guidelines (ANNEX 5) and are encouraged to use the project dissemination material (leaflets, posters, presentations, etc). Finally, photos should be taken and communicated to WP7 leader Q-PLAN, for further dissemination.

A «Future Events» list has already been created by Q-PLAN and is part of the "Dissemination list.xls" document that can be found in the ANNEX 1. The list must be continuously monitored and enriched by all partners.

4.8 CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD workshops and training/demonstration sessions

During the project, four workshops will be organized by pilot partners (COOSS, UHULL, CHU-ROUEN, FUB) with the aim to familiarize all interested parties with the project and platform, and to collect insights from relevant stakeholders to be fed into the design of the platform. The first workshop will take place before M6 (June 2016) under the responsibility of COOS and other workshops will follow after M12 (December 2016), to coincide with the pilots.

Each workshop will be held in the country of the organizer partner and in the local language. Local dissemination campaigns for the workshops will be under the responsibility of the organizer partner, with the support of Q-PLAN for central level dissemination (project web-portal and social media, newsletter and massive e-mail sender tool for dispatch of invitations, press release in English, and promotional material in English). Local dissemination campaigns may include: invitations to local media to take part as speakers, TV appearances, press releases in local press media etc. However, it should be noted again that **partners should produce no kind of promotional material related to the event without the previous review and approval of WP7 leader Q-PLAN.**

An Event Report will be prepared by each partner responsible for organizing a project event and will include photos, list of participants and copies of publications related to the dissemination of the event etc. (ANNEX 6)

4.9 CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD closing event

By the end of the project, a closing event (possibly as a satellite event at a larger international event and preferably in Brussels) will be organized to present the final results of the project and develop networks for future projects. It will be open to the public and will aim to attract policy makers from several European institutions. The partner responsible for the dissemination and organization of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD closing event is Q-PLAN. All partners should contribute to further disseminate the final event through their personal networks.

4.10 Synergies with other projects/ initiatives

Synergies with other EU-funded or international research projects and initiatives in project's research domains will be pursued throughout the project to facilitate knowledge interchange, to gain mutual dissemination benefits and to exploit potential synergies. Possible synergies may include (without being limited to) the following actions:

- Inclusion of the project web-portal and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects,
- Participation in events of similar projects,
- Dissemination of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD promotional material in events of similar projects,
- Invitations to participate in CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD events, and
- Exchange of news/invitations/press releases and dissemination through each projects' channels.

A «Similar projects and initiatives» list has already been created by Q-PLAN and is part of the "Dissemination_list.xls" document. The form of this document can be found in ANNEX 1. Project partners should keep track of all similar projects and initiatives, which might be interested in collaboration, and should regularly enrich the list. All partners should keep in mind that the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD dissemination strategy cannot reach its full potential unless collaboration with similar projects is established.

4.11 EU dissemination channels

The following EU dissemination channels are going to be used during the project:

- **Health National Contact Points (NCPs) network.** National Contact Points provide guidance, practical information, networking and assistance on all aspects of participation in HORIZON 2020.
- **European Enterprise Network (EEN).** The EEN is an EU network of around 600 business support organizations from more than 60 countries, including chambers of commerce and industry, technology centers, research institutes and development agencies.

- **CORDIS** (Community Research and Development Information Service) **WIRE**. CORDIS WIRE is a CORDIS online service that helps disseminating and promoting EU projects' activities by publishing news and events on CORDIS
- **EU Info-days/ Workshops**

The Project Officer will be contacted with regards to possible dissemination steps supported by the EU.

5 Publicity monitoring

Project partners are expected to continuously carry out publicity actions and also continuously report all publicity and communications outcomes. Q-PLAN will be overall responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD dissemination activities.

Reporting of any dissemination activity and publication is expected from partners by completing the “CAREGIVERSPRO-Dissemination activities.xls” and “CAREGIVERSPRO-Publications.xls” documents and sending them to WP7 leader Q-PLAN, at the latest three weeks after the dissemination activity or publication. Especially for participation in external events, partners should follow the respective Guidelines (ANNEX 5). In the case of events organized by the project, the partner responsible for the organization of the event must prepare an Event Report (ANNEX 6) at the latest three weeks after the dissemination activity or publication.

Partners should produce no kind of promotional material related to the project without the previous review and approval of WP7 leader Q-PLAN.

All publications must cite and refer to EU contribution and grant agreement number of the project, as required in Grant Agreement. Examples on how to comply with these requirements can be found in ANNEX 4.

Each project partner should immediately contact Q-PLAN if they identify opportunities, problems or risks arising while planning or implementing publicity actions.

6 Publicity timetable

Activity	Related Work Packages (WP) and milestones	2016						2017					2018						
		January- February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December	January- February	March-April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December	January-February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December
4.1 Web- portal																			
Publicity through project web-portal (Q-PLAN, ALL)	All WPs All milestones																		
4.2 Social media accounts																			
Publicity through Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn (ALL)	All WPs All milestones																		
Publicity through YouTube channel of the project (Q-PLAN)	WP2, WP3, WP5 MS6																		

4.3 Online newsletters																			
Recipients' list creation and update (Q-PLAN)	WP7																		
E- newsletter (6 issues) (Q-PLAN, all)	All WPs All milestones																		
4.4 Promotional material																			
Logo (Q-PLAN)	All WPs All milestones																		
Presentation (Q-PLAN)	WP7																		
Leaflet, poster (Q-PLAN)	WP7																		
Video (Q-PLAN, technical partners)	WP2, WP3, WP5 MS6																		
Promotional material for project events (Q-PLAN, organizers of events)	WP7																		
4.5 Publications in popular/ mass media and scientific publications																			

Press releases (all)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 All milestones																		
Media relations e.g. interviews, articles on CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD in specialized media, mass media etc.(all)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 All milestones																		
Scientific publications (all)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 MS4, MS5, MS6, MS7, MS8, MS9, MS10																		
4.5 Interaction with Social Media Networks of the platform																			
Exchange of news, posts and tweets between social media of the project and of the platform	All WPs All milestones																		
4.6 Participation in external events																			
Exhibitions, business events, information days (all)	WP7																		
Scientific events, conferences etc. (all)	WP7																		

4.7 CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD workshops and training/ demonstration sessions																			
Project workshops (COOS, FUB, CHU-ROUEN, UHULL)	WP4, WP5, WP7 MS3, MS4, MS5, MS6																		
4.8 CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD closing event																			
Project final event (Q-PLAN)	All WPs MS7, MS8, MS9																		
4.9 Synergies with other projects/ initiatives																			
Inclusion in other projects webportal, participation in other projects' events, invitations to participate in CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD events, co-dissemination, exchange of news (Q-PLAN, all)	WP7																		
4.10 EU dissemination channels																			
NCPs network, EEN network, Cordis wire, EU info-days/workshops (Q-PLAN)	WP7																		

7 ANNEX 1 - Dissemination list (template)

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Name	Website	Country	Comments	Partner with personal contact				
Dementia partnerships	www.dementiapartnerships.com	UK	Knowledge and news portal for Dementia, supported by National Clinical Director for Dementia, NHS England					
Alzheimer Europe	www.alzheimer-europe.org	Luxembourg	NGO umbrella organisation of 37 Alzheimer associations from 32 countries.					
European Working Group of People with Dementia	http://www.alzheimer-europe.org/Alzheimer-Europe/Who-we-are/European-Working-Group-of-People-with-Dementia/Current-Members		The European Working Group of People with Dementia - EWGPWD - is composed of people with dementia. They work to ensure that the activities, projects and meetings of Alzheimer Europe duly reflect the priorities and views of people with dementia. The group operates independently, with its own Board and agenda of activities. The Chairperson of the EWGPWD also sits on the Board of Alzheimer Europe.					
Alzheimer Austria	http://www.alzheimer-selbsthilfe.at/	Austria	Twitter:@alzheimerAT					
Ligue Nationale Alzheimer Liga	http://www.alzheimer-belgium.be/en/	Belgium	Old website					
Alzheimer Bulgaria	http://alzheimer-bg.org/	Bulgaria	Website in bulgarian					
Foundation Compassion Alzheimer Bulgaria	http://www.alzheimerbulgaria.org/	Bulgaria						
Alzheimer Croatia	http://www.alzheimer.hr/	Croatia						
Cyprus Alzheimer's Association		Cyprus						
Czech Alzheimer's Society	http://www.alzheimer.cz/	Czech Republic						
Alzheimerforeningen	http://www.alzheimer.dk/	Denmark						
Alzheimer Society of Finland (Muistiliitto)	http://www.muistiliitto.fi/en	Finland	Non-profit organization, two local branches and 43 local associations across the country with around 13000 members altogether					
Association France Alzheimer (France Alzheimer et maladies apparentées)	http://www.francealzheimer.org/	France						
Deutsche Alzheimer Gesellschaft	https://www.deutsche-alzheimer.de/	Germany	The DAIZG provides information about dementia (especially Alzheimer's disease). It is a self-help organisation, which will improve conditions for people suffering from dementia in Germany.					
Panhellenic Federation of Alzheimer's Disease and Related Disorders	http://www.alzheimer-federation.gr/	Greece	Non-profit organization, consists of 35 linked local associations all over Greece					
The Alzheimer Association of Iceland (FAAS)	http://www.alzheimer.is/	Iceland						
The Alzheimer Society of Ireland	http://www.alzheimer.ie/Home.aspx	Ireland	Leading dementia specific service provider in Ireland, 22 branches, 6 regional offices, 33 day care centres, 28 home care/ support services, 28 carer support groups, 3 social clubs, a respite centre, alzheimer national helpline service, accounts 3000 members					
EMDA- The Alzheimer's Association of Israel	http://www.alz-il.net/lang/186-english-2	Israel						
Federazione Alzheimer Italia	http://www.alzheimer.it/	Italy						
Alzheimer Unity Roma Onlus	http://www.alzheimerunity.it	Italy						
Jersey Alzheimer's Association	http://www.jerseyalzheimers.com/	USA						
Association Luxembourg Alzheimer	http://www.alzheimer.lu/	Luxembourg						
Malta Dementia Society	https://sites.google.com/site/maltheademantiasociety/	Malta						
Association Monégasque pour la recherche sur la maladie d'Alzheimer	http://ampa-monaco.com/fr/	Monaco						
Alzheimer Nederland	http://www.alzheimer-nederland.nl/	Netherlands						
Nasjonalforeningen for folkelsen	http://nasjonalforeningen.no/	Norway						
Polskie Stowarzyszenie Pomocy Osobom z Chorobą Alzheimerą	http://www.alzheimer-waw.pl/	Poland						

D7.2 Dissemination plan- first version CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

CAREGIVERSPRO-Dissemination list - Excel

	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T
	Date	Venue	Organizer	Link															
1																			
2	21-24 April 2016	Budapest	ADI	http://www.adi2016.org/															
3	24-28 July 2016	Toronto, Canada		https://www.alz.org/aaic/about/practical-information.asp															
4	29/9-1/10	London, UK		http://alzheimers-dementia.conferenceseries.com/call-for-abstracts.php															
5	5-7 October 2016	Lisbon		http://www.eugms.org/2016.html															
6	31 October- 2 November 2016	Copenhagen																	
7	10 December 2015	Paris	Association Française des aidants																
8	3-6/9/2015	Gothenburg, Sweden	Swedish Family Care Competence Centre, Carers Sweden, Carers UK	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/events/6th-international-carers-conference-care-and-caring-future-proofing-the-new-demographics															
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D7.2 Dissemination plan- first version CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

CAREGIVERSPRO-Dissemination list - Excel

Name	website	Country	Partner with personal contact	Comments					
Care Alliance Ireland	http://www.carealliance.ie/funding	Ireland	Care Alliance Ireland is the National Network of Voluntary Organisations supporting Family Carers. Our vision is that the role of Family Carers is fully recognised and valued by society in Ireland.						
IACO- International alliance of carer organizations	http://www.internationalcarers.org/	USA	A group of national and multinational non-governmental organizations have created a new international organization to investigate and address issues of international family caregiving with the intent of increasing public awareness of the needs of the family caregiver on a global scale. Incorporated in 2012, the International Alliance of Carer Organizations (IACO) serves as an umbrella organization that provides cohesive direction, facilitates information sharing, and actively advocates for carers at an international level.						
Eurocarers-European Association Working for Carers	http://www.eurocarers.org/	Luxembourg	Eurocarers was officially incorporated in Luxembourg in December 2006. The origin of Eurocarers lies in two European networks: Carmen, a network on integrated care and Eurofamcare a research network on carers of older persons. In the Carmen project researchers, practitioners and policy makers, among them representatives of the carers movement, found each other and came to the conclusion that it was time for carers to be heard at European level. The Eurofamcare network consisting of researchers who mapped the situation of carers of older persons and the policy measures developed for this category in the entire EU and who did quantitative research on the support of carers of older persons in 6 countries - also diagnosed a strong need for carers to make themselves heard in Europe.						
Carers UK	www.carersuk.org	UK							
	www.dementiacarer.net								
STADA Arzneimittel	www.stada.com	Germany	publicly traded, international company with a focus on the healthcare market						

HEALTHCARE RESEARCH POLICY SIMILAR EU PROJECTS SOCIAL MEDIA NCPs

D7.2 Dissemination plan- first version
CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

CAREGIVERSPRO-Dissemination list - Excel

Name	website	Country	Partner with personal contact	Comments
University of Liverpool, Ageing research	https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/ageing-research/	UK	Research is focused on biological, medical, psychological and social aspects of ageing. The University fosters interdisciplinary collaborations to help understand the process of ageing as well as help improve the quality of life of a growing elderly population by preventing or delaying the onset of physical or mental decline	
Age Institute	http://www.ikainstituutti.fi/in+english/	Finland	The Age Institute studies the everyday lives of older adults, develops services for older people, produces new innovations for older adults and their families, disseminates information about the results of new studies, offers training to professionals, and participates in current discussion on age related issues, values and attitudes. Research topics: physical exercise, functional capacity and health, encounter, inclusion and mental well-being	
Centre for Healthy Aging (CEHA)-University of Copenhagen	http://healthaging.ku.dk/	Denmark	The CEHA is focused on aging research for the advance of better health and reduced frailty. The center involves five research programs: - Molecular Aging and neurobiology - Skeletal Muscle Metabolism - Body and Life - Society and Culture - Health Promotion and Innovation	
Danish Centre for Molecular Gerontology (DCMG)- University of Aarhus	http://www.dcmg.dk/index.html	Denmark	The aims of the DCMG are to identify molecular and cellular mechanisms involved in the ageing process and in the origin of age-related diseases, to search for effective means of reducing age-related loss in cellular functions, to search for methods for recovery of lost biological activity during ageing, and to employ the knowledge obtained to prevent some of the age-related diseases. International centre with participating laboratories in Aarhus, Vejle, and Baltimore, USA. Research topics: DNA damage Premature ageing syndromes Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease Telomeric-regulation of cellular ageing Gene expression and function with ageing Hormesis	
Centre for Geriatric Medicine and Gerontology (ZGGF)- Medical School, University of Freiburg	https://www.uniklinik-freiburg.de/zggf.html	Germany	The ZGGF is a centre of excellence for the diagnosis and treatment of memory disorders. It provides diagnostic services and takes part in research of dementia. Research topics: Image analysis of the disordered brain	

Navigation tabs: DEMENTIA ASSOCIATIONS-NETWORKS | Future events | HEALTHCARE | **RESEARCH** | POLICY | SIMILAR EU PROJECTS | SOCIAL MEDIA | NCPs

D7.2 Dissemination plan- first version
CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

CAREGIVERSPRO-Dissemination list - Excel

1	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
	Name	website	Country	Partner with personal contact								
2	Social Policy and Ageing Research Centre (SPARC)- Trinity College Dublin- University of Dublin	http://sparc.tcd.ie/index.php	Ireland	SPARC views on research into the social policy impacts and implications of ageing and generates policy advice and insights that can in turn be used by policy makers and practitioners to improve the lives of older people. Research topics: Participation and inclusion of older people - service delivery to community-dwelling older people, analysis of advocacy in long-stay care settings, social engagement and networks of older adults, participation in hospital discharge, subjective experience of dementia Long-term care - analysis of domiciliary care policies and cash-for-care programmes, study of the social and nutritional aspects of community meals provision and utilisation, policy discourse surrounding ageing-related care Older adults interacting with other age and population groups - contributions of older adults in areas such as childcare and voluntary work, study of migrant workers in the elder care sectors								
3	European Union Geriatric Medicine Society (EUGMS)	http://www.eugms.org/home.html	Belgium	The mission of EUGMS is to develop geriatric medicine in the European Union as an independent specialty caring for all older people with age-related disease, to support that these services become available, to promote education and continuing professional development, to promote geriatric medicine to the European Commission and Parliament, and to promote evidence-based guidelines for the most efficacious preventive and treatment strategies for older people in the European Union. Publishes the European Geriatric Medicine Journal								
4	European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing	http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/index_en.cfm?section=active-healthy-ageing										
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DEMENTIA ASSOCIATIONS-NETWORKS Future events HEALTHCARE RESEARCH POLICY SIMILAR EU PROJECTS SOCIAL MEDIA NCPs ... 100%

D7.2 Dissemination plan- first version
CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

CAREGIVERSPRO-Dissemination list - Excel

NAME	Webpage	Notes			
1					
2	https://www.linkedin.com/company/20595937?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Acompany%2CclickedEntityId%3A20595937%2Cid%3A2-2-3%2CtarId%3A1453283440616%2Ctas%3Adementia	We are a Community Interest Company established to provide short breaks & adventure travel for people with dementia and their carers. We also aim to support others to do the same by offering training courses & consultancy services which link to research projects all with nature in mind.			
3	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/1945739/profile				
4	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/126335/profile	By Alzheimer's Association			
5	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8160611/profile				
6	https://www.linkedin.com/company/5096910?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Ashowcase%2CclickedEntityId%3A5096910%2Cid%3A4-1-11%2CtarId%3A1453283440616%2Ctas%3Adementia				
7	https://www.linkedin.com/company/3673977?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Ashowcase%2CclickedEntityId%3A3673977%2Cid%3A4-2-12%2CtarId%3A1453283440616%2Ctas%3Adementia				
8	https://www.linkedin.com/in/dementiacr?authType=NAME_SEARCH&authToken=Q0zE8locaIe=en_US&trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3AmyNetwork%2CclickedEntityId%3A252726912%2CauthType%3ANAME_SEARCH%2Cid%3A5-1-13%2CtarId%3A1453283440616%2Ctas%3Adementia				
9	https://www.linkedin.com/company/867234?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Acompany%2CclickedEntityId%3A867234%2Cid%3A2-1-2%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer				
10	https://www.linkedin.com/company/843464?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Acompany%2CclickedEntityId%3A843464%2Cid%3A2-2-3%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer				
11	https://www.linkedin.com/company/978059?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Acompany%2CclickedEntityId%3A978059%2Cid%3A2-5-6%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer				
12	https://www.linkedin.com/company/10219263?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Ashowcase%2CclickedEntityId%3A10219263%2Cid%3A4-1-11%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer				
13	https://www.linkedin.com/in/alzheimer?authType=NAME_SEARCH&authToken=KB318locaIe=en_US&trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3AmyNetwork%2CclickedEntityId%3A61600788%2CauthType%3ANAME_SEARCH%2Cid%3A5-1-13%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer				
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D7.2 Dissemination plan- first version
CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

CAREGIVERSPRO-Dissemination list - Excel

Organization	website	Country	Name			
FFG - Austrian Research Promotion Agency	http://www.ffg.at	Austria	Astrid Hoebertz	astrid.hoebertz@ffg.at		
Union Wallonne des Entreprises	http://www.ncpwallonie.be	Belgium	Mr François Louesse	francois.louesse@ncpwallonie.be		
The Brussels Enterprise Agency (Impulse Brussels)	http://www.ncpbrussels.be	Belgium	Ms Sarah Van Haelst	svh@impulse.irisnet.be		
Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO) - EUROFED	http://eurofed.stis.belspo.be/	Belgium	Ms Pascale Van Dinter	pascale.vandinter@stis.belspo.be		
Agency for Innovation by Science and Technology (IWT)	http://www.iwt.be	Belgium	Mr Alain Deleener	adf@iwat.be		
Medical University - Varna		Bulgaria	Ms Slava Penova	slava.penova@mu-varna.bg		
Medical University - Sofia		Bulgaria	Chief Assist Prof, PhD, MD Evgeni Zhivkov	ejivkov2000@yahoo.com		
Agency for Mobility and EU Programmes	http://www.mobilnost.hr/	Croatia	Ms Branka Bernard	branka.bernard@mobilnost.hr		
Research Promotion Foundation	http://www.research.org.cy/	Cyprus	Ms Georgia Kleanthous	gkleanthous@research.org.cy		
Technology centre ASCR	http://www.tc.cz/	Czech Republic	Doc, RNDr, CSc Judita Kinkorová	kinkorova@tc.cz		
Danisch Ministry of Science, Innovation and Higher Education, Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation		Denmark	Mr Kim Kryger	klk@fi.dk		
Estonian Research Council	http://www.etag.ee	Estonia	Mr Argo Soon	argo.soon@etag.ee		
Academy of Finland	http://www.aka.fi/eng	Finland	Mr Antti Hautaniemi	antti.hautaniemi@aka.fi		
Tekes	http://www.tekes.fi/en	Finland	Ms Katrina Kippo	katriina.kippo@tekes.fi		
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INSERM - Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale	http://www.inserm.fr/	France	Mr. Nacer Boubenna	nacer.boubenna@inserm.fr		
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CNRS - Centre national de recherche scientifique	http://www.protisvalor.com/site/fr/contrats_eu	France	Mrs Véra Frassetto	vera.frassetto@cnrs-dir.fr		
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BPI France Financement	http://www.bpifrance.fr/	France	Mrs Marielle Mailhes	marielle.mailhes@bpifrance.fr		
INSERM - Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale	http://www.inserm.fr/	France	Mr Nacer Boubenna	pcn-fet@recherche.gouv.fr		
MENESR - Ministère de l'éducation nationale, de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche	http://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr	France	Mr Guillaume Fusai	guillaume.fusai@recherche.gouv.fr		
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D7.2 Dissemination plan- first version
CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

CAREGIVERSPRO-Dissemination list - Excel

Centre For Interdisciplinary And Multidisciplinary Research And Studies Of The University Of Maribor - See more at: <http://een.ec.europa.eu/about/sector-groups/healthcare#tshash.7Goyzy40.dpuf>

Name	Country	Organization	E-mail
Hicham Abghay	Germany	Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum	abghay@steinbeis-europa.de
Beatriz Pérez	Spain	Fundación Parque Científico De Madrid	transferencia.tecnologia@fpcm.es
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Juan-J. Carmona-Schneider	Germany	Zenit Zentrum Für Innovation Und Technik Nordrhein-Westfalen - See more at: http://een.ec.europa.eu/about/sector-groups/healthcare#tshash.7Goyzy40.dpuf	jc@zenit.de
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Fatih Sarac	Turkey	Samsun Chamber of Commerce and Industry	fsarac@samsuntso.org.tr
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Simone Strathoff	Germany	Zenit Zentrum Für Innovation Und Technik Nordrhein-Westfalen - See more at: http://een.ec.europa.eu/about/sector-groups/healthcare#tshash.7Goyzy40.dpuf	SH@zenit.de
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Nevan Tamarut	Croatia	Science and Technology Park of the University of Rijeka - See more at: http://een.ec.europa.eu/about/sector-groups/healthcare#tshash.7Goyzy40.dpuf	ntamarut@uniri.hr
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Anna Wrzesinska	Poland	Podlaska Regional Development Foundation	wrzesinska@pfrf.pl
Matthias Wurch	Germany	Leibniz Universität Hannover	matthias.wurch@zuv.uni-hannover.de

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Greece-Agenda.docx updated
"Greece-Agenda.docx" was updated to the latest version (click to view).

10 ANNEX 4 - EU requirements on dissemination of results (as set in Grant Agreement)

Any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic), must:

- Display the EU emblem with appropriate prominence
- Include the following text: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690211”*

In applications for protecting results (including patent applications), the following text must be included: *“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690211”*

In reports and deliverables of public dissemination level, the following disclaimer must also be included: *“The current report reflects only the author’s view and the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD CONSORTIUM and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”*

Each beneficiary must ensure Open Access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

- As soon as possible and at latest on publication, deposit a machine readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications
- Ensure Open Access to the deposited publication –via the repository- at the latest:
 - i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher or
 - ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in social sciences and humanities) in any other case
- Ensure Open Access –via the repository- to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms European Union (EU) and Horizon 2020,
- The name of the project, acronym and grant number,
- The publication date, and length of embargo period (if any), and
- A persistent identifier.

11 ANNEX 5- Guidelines for partners reporting participation in external events

Partners participating in external events (exhibitions, business events, information days, scientific events and conferences, *etc.*) should comply with the following:

- Before the event, please complete “Dissemination list.xls” (sheet «Future Events») with the required information about the event.
- If you are going to make a presentation, please use the general project presentation and make any modifications necessary to this file, keeping the same template.
- During the event, please use the project dissemination material (leaflets, posters *etc.*).
- Please do not forget to take photos.
- Update the Dissemination Leader (Q-PLAN) with your participation in the event and share the photos taken, not later than ten days after the event.
- Please complete “Dissemination activities.xls” with all required information about your participation in the event at the latest three weeks after the event.

12 ANNEX 6- Event's report (template)

EVENT'S-REPORT

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690211"

Project Number	690211	Acronym	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD
Full title	Self-management interventions and mutual assistance community services, helping patients with dementia and caregivers connect with others for evaluation, support and inspiration to improve the care experience		
Project coordinator	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya- BarcelonaTech Prof. Ulises Cortés, ia@cs.upc.edu		
Project URL	http://www.caregiversprommd-project.eu		

Authors (Partner)	Author1 (Partner1), Author2 Partner2),		
Responsible Author	Author 1	Email	
	Partner	Phone	

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3 EVALUATION OF THE EVENT	4
4 ANNEXES	4
4.1 AGENDA	4
4.2 LIST OF PARTICIPANTS (NAMES AND SIGNATURES IF POSSIBLE)	4
4.3 PHOTOS	4
4.4 PRESENTATIONS	4

1 Event Aggregate Data

	Title	
	Date	
	Venue	
	Audience (number and type)	
	Duration	

2 Structure of the event (short minutes)

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3 Evaluation of the event

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4 ANNEXES

4.1 Agenda

4.2 List of participants (names and signatures if possible)

4.3 Photos¹

4.4 Presentations

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¹ In case of photos of persons participating in pilots of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD, their appropriate consent for publishing their photos must first be asked.